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Pesticides and copper report (I)

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1. Executive Summary

This document aims to highlight the pesticides used in Mediterranean olive groves, focusing on the diagnosis across three types of olive cultivation: organic (ORG, the highest environmental standard for olive grove cultivation in Europe), traditional (TD, the type of cultivation most widespread olive grove cultivation in the Mediterranean region) and high-density (HD, modern agriculture applied to olive cultivation in clear expansion worldwide). A total of 53 orchards have been sampled and 494 samples have been analysed. In the Soil O-Live initial Document of Agreement (DoA), three target compounds were selected and identified: copper, oxyfluorfen (pre-emergence herbicide), and glyphosate (post-emergent herbicide). Furthermore, this diagnostic stage has been extended to other pesticides, including 28 fungicides, 22 herbicides, and 12 insecticides, in order to increase awareness of their presence and improve the understanding of the prevalence of pesticides in Mediterranean olive grove soils. The different analytical methods used are described in this document.

Regarding copper, all samples have tested positive with random copper content (from 3.99 to 768.69 mg/kg) and with Spanish orchards having the highest average value, followed by Italy, Greece, Morocco, and Portugal. Depending on the type of crop, the overall amount of copper varies in the order ORG>TD>HD in Spain, Italy and Greece, whereas in Morocco the copper content in ORG orchards is lower. Additionally, it is important to shed light on the presence of strongly retained copper which could affect the selection of the remediation strategy.

Regarding glyphosate, 27 % of the samples were positives (with detected concentrations over 0.05 µg/kg (LoQ)) whereas 44 % of samples were positives in AMPA, which is a metabolite of glyphosate and thus, its presence is related to the use of glyphosate. Portugal and Spain show the highest values, mainly in TD and HD orchards.

Regarding the organic pesticides, close to 55 % of the samples have been detected positive for at least one pesticide. The highest presence of oxyfluorfen is observed in TD orchards in Greece and HD orchards in Spain. Propiconazole and trifloxystrobin are also detected in more than 10% of total samples, being present in the 25 % of the positives in ORG samples. Diflufenican, an herbicide, is also detected recurrently in HD samples.

2. Experimental

A total of 494 samples have been analysed. The sampled orchards correspond with different types of crops: Traditional (TD), High Density (HD), and Organic (ORG), from the following countries: Spain, Portugal, Morocco, Italy, and Greece.

- Spain – 159 samples from 17 orchards
- Greece – 149 samples from 15 orchards
- Portugal – 50 samples from 5 orchards
- Italy – 66 from 9 orchards
- Morocco- 70 samples from 7 orchards

Soil samples were taken following LUCAS protocol (Fernandez-Ugalde, 2022). From each orchard, 5 sampling points were set at two horizons: 0-10 cm and 10-20 cm. Additionally, 15 additional samples were

taken in the 0-20 cm horizon in a selected Spanish orchard to carry out a homogeneity study to ensure that samples collected at different locations within the orchard represent the pollution level of the entire olive grove.

The orchards were classified using an alphanumeric coding system, with the first two letters indicating the country code (ES/GR/PT/IT/MR), the following letters indicating the type of crop (TD/HD/ORG) and the numbers indicating the specific orchards. Table 1 shows the codification of the orchards sampled.

Table 1. Classification of orchards

Traditional	High-density	Organic
ES-TD1	ES-HD10	ES-ORG11
ES-TD15	ES-HD2	ES-ORG12
ES-TD5	ES-HD22	ES-ORG13
ES-TD7	ES-HD3	ES-ORG14
ES-TD9*	ES-HD40	ES-ORG4
GR-TD30	ES-HD8	ES-ORG6
GR-TD31	GR-HD43	GR-ORG32
GR-TD35	MR-HD25	GR-ORG33
GR-TD36	MR-HD28	GR-ORG34
GR-TD37	PT-HD51	GR-ORG38
GR-TD44	PT-HD52	GR-ORG39
GR-TD46	PT-HD53	GR-ORG45
IT-TD16**		GR-ORG47
IT-TD20**		IT-ORG17**
IT-TD21		IT-ORG18**
IT-TD50**		IT-ORG19**
MR-TD24		IT-ORG48*
MR-TD26		IT-ORG49*
MR-TD27		MR-ORG23
MR-TD29		
PT-TD41		
PT-TD42		

*Only 4 sampling points were received from this orchard

**Only 3 sampling points were received from these orchards

Samples were received as collected (Figure 1) and they had to be conditioned following the procedure of drying, crushing, and sieving summarized in Figure 2.

Fig. 1. Sample reception.

Fig. 2. Sample conditioning.

2.1 Copper analysis for soils

The analysis of copper in soil samples were carried out by two different methods. On one side, the total concentration of copper in soil was evaluated using the standard method ISO 11466:1995 Soil quality - Extraction of trace elements soluble in *aqua regia*. A sample aliquot of 3 g (air-dried) was mixed with 1 mL of water to moisten the sample. After that, the sample was mixed with *aqua regia* (21 mL of hydrochloric acid and 7 mL of nitric acid) as an extraction solution to allow the oxidation of organic content. Both phases were stirred for 16 h at room temperature. Then, the mixture was left on reflux for 2h. Then, the samples were centrifugated and filtered. On the other hand, an alternative method without reflux (only extraction during 16 h with *aqua regia*) was also used to determine the copper concentration less fixed in soil. Finally, the copper concentration in the liquid phase was measured by Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS). Table 2 shows the main analytical features of the method.

Table 2. Analytical figures of merit

Precision (RSD)	0.6–2.4 %
Linear range	2.4–48.3 mg/kg
Limits of quantification (LoQ)	2.4 mg/kg
Limits of detection (LoD)	1.2 mg/kg

2.2 Glyphosate and AMPA determination

The presence of Glyphosate (GLY) and Aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA) in soil samples was determined by performing solid-liquid extraction and purification using a QuEChERS procedure adapted for soils. Their determination relies on the process of derivatization due to the high polarity of these compounds, modifying their structures to increase their chromatography separation and sensitivity, allowing the determination of the compounds at lower concentrations. Then, liquid chromatography – tandem mass spectrometry is employed for the determination of the pesticides. A sample of 2 g (air-dried) were mixed with 10 mL of a KOH solution (0.6 M) as extractant solution. Both phases were shaken for 60 min and then centrifugate for 30 min at 3500 rpm. Afterwards, 1 mL of supernatant was mixed with 80 µL of HCl (6 M) obtaining approx. a pH ~9, and then, the derivatization process was carried out adding 40 µL of isotopically labelled standards of glyphosate and AMPA (5 mg/L), 0.5 mL of borate buffer, 25 mM pH 9.2 in ACN (30:70 v/v) and 0.5 mL of 9-FMOC-Cl (6.5 mM in ACN). Finally, the samples were vortexed and allow for 30 min to complete the reaction. The supernatant is injected in the liquid chromatography tandem mass-spectrometry (HPLC-Qtrap MS/MS) in electrospray ionization mode (ESI) in negative mode (ESI-). Table 3 shows the analytical characteristics of the method.

Table 3. Analytical figures of merit

Recoveries	79.4-126.5 %
Precision (RSD)	2.9-4.5 %
Linear range	0.05 – 500 µg/Kg
Limits of quantification (LoQ)	0.05 µg/Kg
Limits of detection (LoD)	0.015 µg/Kg

2.3. General multi-residue extraction of pesticides

The presence of different pesticides (63) in soil samples was determined by performing a solid-liquid extraction using a QuEChERS procedure. In this process, 5 g of air-dried sample was mixed with 10 mL of water to enhance the mass transference between the solid and the liquid, and 10 mL of ACN containing 1 % acetic acid (ACN 1% HAc) as extractant. Sodium acetate (CH₃COONa, 1 g) and magnesium sulphate (MgSO₄, 4g) were added as salts to obtain better extraction by the solvent. The sample was shaken to increase the contact for 60 min and then centrifugate for 30 min at 3500 rpm. The supernatant is injected in a liquid chromatography tandem mass-spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) in electrospray ionization mode (ESI) both in positive and negative mode (ESI+, ESI-). The methodology provided the following analytical properties:

Table 4. Analytical figures of merit.

Recoveries	40-108 %
Precision (RSD)	6-18 %
Linear range	0.05 – 500 µg/Kg
Limits of quantification (LoQ)	0.05 µg/Kg
Limits of detection (LoD)	0.015 µg/Kg

Apart from oxyfluorfen and glyphosate, which were initially selected as target pesticides, the scope of the method was extended to cover a larger variety of pesticide classes (Table 5).

Table 5. Analysed pesticides.

Family	Compound	Family	Compound	Family	Compound
Fungicides	Boscalid	Herbicides	Atrazine	Insecticides	Carbaryl
	Bromuconazole Isomer 1		Atrazine desethyl		Carbofuran
	Bromuconazole Isomer 2		Atrazine desisopropyl		Chlorpyrifos ethyl
	Carbendazim		Chloridazon (Pyrazon)		Chlorpyrifos methyl
	Cymoxanil		Desethyl-terbutylazine		Clothianidin
	Cyproconazole		Diflufenican		Ethion
	Cyprodinil		Dimethenamid		Imidacloprid
	Difenoconazole		Diuron		Malathion
	Dimethomorph E		Flufenacet		Parathion
	Dimethomorph Z		Fluroxypyr		Parathion-methyl
	Dimoxystrobin		Imazamox		Pirimicarb
	Epoxiconazole		Isoxaben		Pirimiphos methyl
	Fenpropidine		Lenacil		
	Fenpropimorphe		Linuron		
	Fluquinconazole		Metamitron		
	Imazalil		Metolachlor		
	Isoproturon		Oxifluorfen		
	Metalaxyl		Prosulfocarb		
	Myclobutanil		Simazine		
	Penconazole		Terbutylazine		
	Prochloraz		Terbutryn		
	Propiconazole		Triallat		
	Pyraclostrobin				
	Quinoxyfen				
	Thiabendazole				
	Thiophanate-methyl				
Triadimenol					
Trifloxystrobin					

3. Results

A summary of the results obtained in the determination of the three target compounds is presented in this section. We included the species initially flagged in the document of activities (copper, glyphosate, and oxyfluorfen). Additionally, and to have a wider view of the pollution scenario, the analysis has been extended to other compounds: AMPA (metabolite of glyphosate) and other commonly used organic pesticides (Table 5). The complete results will be available in the *dataset UCLM_UJA_OPEN_Pesticides Copper Data SOIL O-LIVE PROJECT 2024 RP1* (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.12821804). The dataset will be in restricted mode on the Zenodo platform until the publication of scientific papers, at which point access will be changed to open access.

3.1 Copper content

Regarding copper, all samples have tested positive with random copper content. Table 6 shows the minimum and maximum values of copper content (mg of copper/kg of soil), as well as the average, determined in the orchards of the different sampled countries.

Table 6. Summary of the maximum, minimum, and average concentration of copper in olive grove soils by country.

	Value	Cu (mg/kg)	
		ISO method	Alternative method
Spain (ES)	Min	12.94	7.83
	Max	768.69	397.92
	Average	66.65	37.86
Morocco (MR)	Min	6.66	4.38
	Max	88.55	89.53
	Average	32.51	23.19
Italy (IT)	Min	9.94	7.14
	Max	184.83	134.94
	Average	62.95	43.94
Greece (GR)	Min	9.40	7.97
	Max	312.43	298.68
	Average	46.94	36.44
Portugal (PT)	Min	3.99	1.94
	Max	65.64	28.49
	Average	26.79	14.78

As can be observed, the mean copper concentration of SOIL O-live samples in the topsoil (0-20cm) is 50.9 mg kg⁻¹, ranging from 3.99 to 768.69 mg/kg, with Spanish orchards having the highest average value, followed by Italy, Greece, Morocco, and Portugal using the ISO method. These values are higher than the EU-27 average soil Cu concentration (Panagos et al., 2022) and those reported previously for European olive orchards (Ballabio et al., 2018).

Due to this random copper content, a homogeneity study was also carried out in a Spanish traditional orchard. Figure 3 shows the average copper content of each sample point. Each sample point was measured by triplicate. In this orchard, the copper concentration ranges between 25.5 and 47.2 mg/kg, with an average value of 34.2 mg/kg and a standard deviation of 7.0 mg/kg. This confirms that within the orchard there could be some dispersion, but the number of sampling points is sufficient to have a good evaluation of the pollution level of the entire olive grove.

Fig. 3. Copper concentration in 15 sampling points (horizon 0-20 cm) taken in a traditional Spanish orchard. Analytical method: ■ Alternative method; ■ ISO method.

For comparison purposes, results obtained with the alternative method (without digestion) are also included in Table 6 and Figure 3. **This method is not used for quantification purposes but to shed light on the presence of strongly retained copper which could affect the selection of the remediation strategy (for this reason, alternative method data were not included in dataset).** As expected, there are market differences between results obtained with both methods, which confirms that in many cases there is a copper fraction strongly fixed to the soil matrix and will be difficult to remove using conventional remediation techniques. This fact could be related to the composition of copper-based products and the increasingly frequent use of formulations with low water solubility, such as Cu hydroxide and Cu oxychloride.

Figure 4 shows the copper concentration distribution as function of type of orchard and country in the global horizon of 0-20 cm.

Fig. 4. Copper concentration distribution as function of type of orchard and country in the global horizon of 0-20 cm. ■ TD, ■ ORG, ■ HD.

As can be observed, there are significant differences in the detected copper concentrations based on the type of cultivation and country. Depending on the type of crop, the overall amount of copper varies in the order ORG>TD>HD in Spain, Italy and Greece, whereas in Morocco the copper content in ORG orchards is lower.

Within the ORGs, copper content of orchards located in Spain and Italy oscillates between 20 and 110 mg/kg. In Greece, some orchards present very high specific copper values (200, 180, 160, 120 mg/kg), above the average value of the country (55 mg/kg).

In TD orchards, the great dispersion in the orchards of Spain stands out, with specific values that reach 770 mg/kg, although the majority of orchards has copper values around 25-45 mg/kg. In Italy, Morocco, Greece and Portugal there are values ranging between 15-75 mg/kg, 15-50 mg/kg, 20-45 mg/kg and 35-40 mg/kg, respectively.

In HD crops, the differences between the countries are smaller and Greece orchards present the highest values, ranging between 20-50 mg/kg. On contrary, Portugal orchards have the lowest copper content 30-40 mg/kg.

Figure 5 shows the average value of the two sampled horizons: 0-10 cm and 10-20 cm. As can be observed, the amount of copper accumulated in the upper zone is slightly higher than in the lower zone, independently of the country and type of orchards. This is what was expected due to the most common way to apply copper-based fungicides to olive trees is through foliar sprays. This means that copper does not easily percolate through the soil matrix.

As stated before, the concentration range is huge: 2-600 mg/kg. For a better understanding of the problematic, it has been arbitrarily subdivided into 6 levels: 0-5, 5-15, 15-30, 30-50, 50-150, >150 mg of copper/kg of soil.

Figure 6 shows the dispersion of copper positives in these six concentration ranges in the traditional, high-density and organic orchards, respectively.

In TD orchards, values are above 5 mg/kg. In Spain, around 8% of samples are above 150 mg/kg. Paying attention to samples with values above 50 mg/kg, Italy presents 72% of samples, followed by Morocco with 23%, Spain with 22%, Greece with 17% and Portugal with only 5%. Within 30 and 50 mg/kg, the percentages range between 30% from Greece and 70% from Portugal. Finally, Morocco shows the highest percentage of samples within 5 and 15 mg/kg.

In ORG, there is a higher percentage of samples above 50 mg/kg, except Morocco with 100% of samples in the range 15-50 mg/kg.

Finally, in HD, there is a very high percentage of samples ranging between 15 and 50 mg/kg. The lowest values have been detected in Portugal, with 7% of the samples below 5 mg/kg.

Fig. 5. Copper concentration distribution as function of type of orchard and country in the horizons of 0-10 cm and 10-20 cm. ■ TD, ■ ORG, ■ HD.

Fig. 6. Percentages of samples within each concentration range: ■ 0-5, ■ 5-15, ■ 15-30, ■ 30-50, ■ 50-150, ■ >150 mg of copper/kg of soil.

3.2 Glyphosate and AMPA content

Regarding glyphosate, 27 % of the samples were positives (with detected concentrations over 0.05 µg/kg (LoQ)) whereas 44 % of samples were positives in AMPA, which is a metabolite of glyphosate and thus, its presence is related to the use of glyphosate. Table 7 shows the maximum concentration of both compounds detected as function of the country and type of orchard and Figures 7 and 8 show the distribution of glyphosate and AMPA concentration.

Table 7. Summary of the maximum concentration detected of glyphosate and AMPA (µg/kg)

	Compound	TD	ORG	HD
Spain (ES)	AMPA	115	85.4	284
	Glyphosate	286	28.6	718
Morocco (MR)	AMPA	18.9	N.D.	214
	Glyphosate	N.D. ¹	N.D.	33.2
Italy (IT)	AMPA	N.D.	N.D.	No samples
	Glyphosate	N.D.	N.D.	No samples
Greece (GR)	AMPA	144	72.7	N.D.
	Glyphosate	174	80.8	N.D.
Portugal (PT)	AMPA	572	No samples	1176
	Glyphosate	648	No samples	866

¹N.D.: Not detected

Fig. 7. Glyphosate concentration distribution as function of type of orchard and country in the horizon of 0-20 cm. ■ TD, ■ ORG, ■ HD.

Fig. 8. AMPA concentration distribution as function of type of orchard and country in the horizon of 0-20 cm. ■ TD, ■ ORG, ■ HD.

In general, AMPA is detected in a large number of samples and at a higher average concentration than glyphosate. First, it should be noted that the samples from Italy do not contain neither glyphosate nor AMPA. However, due to insufficient soil sample, the analysis of these compounds in the orchards IT-TD21, IT-ORG48, IT-ORG49 was not possible. Portugal and Spain show the highest values. The concentration of both compounds is similar in TD and HD orchards in Portugal, whereas in Spanish orchards residual levels of glyphosate and AMPA are higher in HD compared to TD orchards. For ORG orchards, the number of positives is lower with 3 for glyphosate and 14 % for AMPA. In contrast, HD orchards have a positive detection over 80 %.

Regarding the distribution of both compounds in the two horizons, Table 8 shows the prevalence percentages of glyphosate and AMPA in each horizon, calculated based on positive samples only. As observed, regardless of the type of cultivation, AMPA is present in more orchards than glyphosate: 71.4 % vs 28.6 % in TD, 73.9 vs 26.1 % in ORG and 51.2 vs 48.8%. Notably, TD orchards in Italy do not contain either compound, and in Morocco, only AMPA is detected.

In organic orchards, Spain and Greece show positive results in AMPA and glyphosate, while these compounds are not detected in Morocco and Italy. In Spanish orchards, the compounds are more frequently found in samples from the first horizon (0-10 cm), whereas in Greek orchards, they appear in both horizons in equal proportions. Regarding both compounds, AMPA appears in more samples than glyphosate: 70.6% and 83.3% for Greece and Spain orchards, respectively.

In HD orchards, AMPA and glyphosate are detected in Morocco, Spain and Portugal, but not in Greece. It's noteworthy that all 30 samples from Portugal and 60 samples from Spain across both horizons tested positive for AMPA and glyphosate, except for one sample from Spain which was negative for glyphosate. In Morocco, a higher number of positive samples appear in the first horizon (0-10 cm), with AMPA detected in more samples than glyphosate.

Table 8. Presence of AMPA and glyphosate by percentage in the different countries and their prevalence by horizons.

TD	All	Morocco	Greece	Spain	Italy	Portugal
	% over total	% over total				
AMPA	71.4	100.0	75.7	63.5	N.D. ¹	67.7
Glyphosate	28.6	0.0	24.3	36.5	N.D.	32.3
% 0-10 cm	60.0	33.3	60.7	69.7	N.D.	50.0
% 10-20 cm	40.0	66.7	39.3	30.3	N.D.	50.0

ORG	All	Morocco	Greece	Spain	Italy	Portugal
	% over total					
AMPA	73.9	N.D.	70.6	83.3	N.D.	-
Glyphosate	26.1	N.D.	29.4	16.7	N.D.	-
% 0-10 cm	60.9	N.D.	47.1	83.3	N.D.	-
% 10-20 cm	39.1	N.D.	52.9	16.7	N.D.	-

HD	All	Morocco	Greece	Spain	Italy	Portugal
	% over total					
AMPA	51.2	63.6	N.D.	50.5	-	50.0
Glyphosate	48.8	36.4	N.D.	49.5	-	50.0
% 0-10 cm	51.8	72.7	N.D.	50.5	-	50.0
% 10-20 cm	48.2	27.3	N.D.	49.5	-	50.0

¹N.D.: Not detected

3.3 Oxyfluorfen and other organic pesticide content

Regarding the organic pesticides, close to 55 % of the samples have been detected positive (concentrations over 0.05 µg/kg (LoQ)) for at least one pesticide. In general, it has been observed a high dispersion among the 5 sampling points within an orchard, making it challenging to draw definitive conclusions beyond general trends regarding total concentrations observed thus far. Table 9 shows the higher concentration of the target compound, oxyfluorfen, which was detected in 8% of the analysed samples. Additionally, it includes the maximum concentration of pesticides detected in at least 10% of the analysed samples, along with the pesticide found in the highest concentration (highlighted in red). The distribution of oxyfluorfen by type of orchards and by country is also illustrated in Figure 9.

Table 9. Summary of the maximum detected concentration of oxyfluorfen and other pesticides detected by multiresidue method in olive orchard soils (µg/kg).

	Compound	TD	HD	ORG
Spain (ES)	Oxyfluorfen:	N.D ¹	95.1	N.D
	Others:	Diflufenican: 28.2 Propiconazole: N.D. Trifloxystrobin: 0.84	Diflufenican: 76.4 Propiconazole: N.D Trifloxystrobin: N.D	Diflufenican: 65.0 Propiconazole: 12.6 Trifloxystrobin: 35.5 Difenoconazole: 99.6
Morocco (MR)	Oxyfluorfen:	94.3	N.D	N.D
	Others:	Diflufenican: N.D. Propiconazole: 2.42 Trifloxystrobin: N.D.	Diflufenican: N.D Propiconazole: N.D Trifloxystrobin: N.D Bromuconazole Isomer 1: 0.56	Diflufenican: N.D. Propiconazole: N.D. Trifloxystrobin: 4.93 Dimoxystrobin: 24.3
Italy (IT)	Oxyfluorfen:	3.27	No samples	N.D
	Others:	Diflufenican: N.D. Propiconazole: N.D. Trifloxystrobin: N.D. Lenacil: 4.66		Diflufenican: N.D. Propiconazole: 10.2 Trifloxystrobin: 10.5 Dimoxystrobin: 31.0
Greece (GR)	Oxyfluorfen:	94.92 µg/kg	N.D	12.29 µg/kg
	Others:	Diflufenican: 0.60 Propiconazole: N.D. Trifloxystrobin: N.D. Lenacil: 6.18	Diflufenican: N.D Propiconazole: N.D Trifloxystrobin: N.D Boscalid: 2.72	Diflufenican: 2.95 Propiconazole: 9.57 Trifloxystrobin: 20.8 Fluroxypyr: 84.3
Portugal (PT)	Oxyfluorfen:	N.D	17.3	No samples
	Others:	Diflufenican: 18.5 Propiconazole: N.D. Trifloxystrobin: N.D. Lenacil: 22.3	Diflufenican: 90.2 Propiconazole: N.D Trifloxystrobin: N.D	

¹N.D.: Not detected

Fig. 9. Oxyfluorfen concentration distribution as function of type of orchard and country in the horizon of 0-20 cm. ■ TD, ■ ORG, ■ HD.

Regarding oxyfluorfen, it's important to note that while there are positive detections in all countries, the distribution varies significantly. The highest presence of oxyfluorfen is observed in TD orchards in Greece and HD orchards in Spain, whereas only a few samples tested positive in other countries (1 sample each in Morocco and Italy, and 2 samples in Portugal). Concerning the presence of other pesticides, propiconazole and trifloxystrobin are also detected in more than 10% of total samples and being present in the 25 % of the positives in ORG samples. Diflufenican, an herbicide, is also detected recurrently in HD samples.

Table 10 shows the distribution of the pesticide detected in the samples, grouped by type of pesticide: fungicide, herbicide and insecticide (see Table 5). As in Table 8, percentage are calculated considering only the positive samples.

In general, among TD soils, 14 out of 63 pesticides are detected in the 0-10 cm horizon and 3 out of 63 for the samples of 10-20 cm horizon. When analysing the results based on pesticide families and countries, variations in the detected groups become evident. None sample of TD orchards are positive to any insecticide. In Morocco, Greece, Italy and Portugal, the presence of herbicides and fungicides are similar, between 40-60 % of each one. However, in the case of Spain, more than the 75 % of positives responses corresponded to herbicides. Moreover, the percentage of positives responses is higher in the 0-10 cm horizon, except for Spain, which presents a similar percentage in both horizons (slightly higher in the 0-10 cm horizon).

From the samples of organic orchards, 32 out of 63 pesticides are detected in the 0-10 cm samples and 11 out of 63 in the 10-20 cm samples. Unlike TD orchards, in this type of orchards a small number of samples (less than 6 %) resulted positives in at least one insecticide. In general, fungicide family present a higher percentage of positive responses than herbicides. It is notable that in all countries, more than the 84 % of positive responses correspond to samples from the 0-10 cm horizon.

Regarding HD soils, 15 out of 63 pesticides are detected in 0-10 cm samples and 17 out of 63 in the 10-20 cm samples. There are significant differences in pesticide family distributions among the countries. Spain and Portugal show a similar distribution, with herbicides being the most detected (more than 50 %). In contrast, they represent only 25.0 % of the positives in Greece and 33.3 % of the positives in Morocco, where the most detected compounds are fungicides (75.0 % and 66.7 % of positives, respectively).

Table 10. Summarized data about presence of pesticides families by percentage in the different countries and their prevalence by horizons.

TD	All	Morocco	Greece	Spain	Italy	Portugal
	% over total					
Fungicide	45.6	46.2	59.5	22.9	50.0	55.6
Herbicide	54.4	53.8	40.5	77.1	50.0	44.4
Insecticide	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
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% 0-10 cm	79.8	100.0	95.2	54.3	100.0	72.2
% 10-20 cm	20.2	0.0	4.8	45.7	0.0	27.8

ORG	All	Morocco	Greece	Spain	Italy	Portugal
	% over total					
Fungicide	54.5	57.1	63.5	44.8	57.9	-
Herbicide	39.7	42.9	34.9	46.3	31.6	-
Insecticide	5.8	0.0	1.6	9.0	10.5	-
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% 0-10 cm	87.8	100.0	84.1	91.0	84.2	-
% 10-20 cm	12.2	0.0	15.9	9.0	15.8	-

HD	All	Morocco	Greece	Spain	Italy	Portugal
	% over total					
Fungicide	36.3	66.7	75.0	31.3	-	40.0
Herbicide	54.1	33.3	25.0	54.2	-	57.8
Insecticide	9.6	0.0	0.0	14.5	-	2.2
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% 0-10 cm	53.3	33.3	0.0	53.0	-	60.0
% 10-20 cm	46.7	66.7	100.0	47.0	-	40.0

Finally, Figures 10-12 illustrate the dispersion of pesticides in the two different horizons per country. It has been observed that certain pesticides may be found in either the 0-10 cm or 10-20 cm horizon depending on the soil type and country of origin.

In Figure 10 can be seen that lenacil and oxyfluorfen have been detected in 4 of the countries, but no pesticide is detected in all countries. Moreover, most of the pesticides are detected only in the first horizon, whereas others such as diflufenican or trifloxystrobin appear only in the 10-20 cm horizon. Lenacil is the only one that appears in both horizons in Greece and Portugal orchards.

The same trend is observed in HD orchards (Figure 11), being some pesticides only detected in the first horizon (0-10 cm), such as bromuconazole, carbendazim, or triadimenol. However, other pesticides such as malathion appear only in the horizon 10-20 cm. As can be seen, lower number of compounds are detected in Greece and Morocco. It is worth mentioning that fluroxypyr is present in three of the four analysed countries (Spain, Greece and Portugal).

Regarding Figure 12, ORG orchards show a high number of different pesticides detected, with Morocco having the lowest number among the countries. Furthermore, in ORG orchards, all samples appear positives in atrazine desethyl, dimoxystrobin, myclobutanil, thiabendazole, triphanate-methyl and trifloxystrobin, showing the appearance of the same pesticides in organic orchards independently of the country analysed. However, under Regulation (EC) No 2018/8483, none of these analytes are permitted in organic farming. Pesticides display dynamic behaviour in the environment, being deposited in soils and plants and dispersed by various factors such as rain and wind. Although organic soils generally have lower pesticide levels than conventional soils, residual contamination can still impact products due to these environmental dynamics. Establishing residue concentration thresholds, as suggested by Schleiffer et al. (2022), is essential to address this issue.

Fig. 10. Percentage of positive results of pesticide in TD orchards by country (Morocco (MR), Spain (ES), Greece (Gr), Italy (IT), Portugal (PT))

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Fig. 11. Percentage of positive results of pesticide in HD orchards by country (Portugal (PT), Greece (Gr), Spain (ES), Morocco (MR))

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Fig. 12. Percentage of positive results of pesticide in ORG orchards by country (Morocco (MR), Spain (SP), Italy (IT), Greece (Gr))

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